

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERISTICS OF THEATER AND CONCERT MANAGEMENT

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada O'zbekistonda teatr va konsert tomoshalari rivojlanishi va uni boshqaruv jarayonidagi o'ziga xos xususiyatlar yoritilgan. Art menejment tamoyillari asosida boshqarishni tashkil etish tizimiga misollar keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: konsert, rejissura, teatr, madaniyat va san'at, art menejment, boshqaruv, marketing, tamoyillar, studiyalar, konsert tashkilotlari.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассмотрено развитие театрально-концертного исполнительства в Узбекистане и особенности управления им. Приведены примеры системы организации управления, основанной на принципах арт-менеджмента.

Ключевые слова: концерт, режиссура, театр, культура и искусство, арт-менеджмент, менеджмент, маркетинг, принципы, студии, концертные организации.

Abstract: This article describes the development of theater and concert performances in Uzbekistan and the specific features of its management. Examples of management organization system based on art management principles are given.

Key words: concert, directing, theater, culture and art, art management, management, marketing, principles, studios, concert organizations.

The political, economic, and cultural changes taking place in our society due to independence have an impact on theater and concert art. The fact that the development of Uzbek Theater is considered a task of state importance is the reason for the further development of work in this direction. The Decree of the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan I.Karimov "On the Development of Uzbek Theater Art" signed in 1998 was an important document that defined the perspective of the national theater art. Over the past five years, a number of decisions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Cabinet of Ministers have been signed on the development of theater and concert

organizations. [1] In particular, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 27, 2018 "On measures to organize the activities of the State Philharmonic of Uzbekistan" No. PQ-3813, December 27, 2021 "Opera and ballet art" PQ-64 on measures for the further development of the theater" and the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers on April 5, 2017 "On perfect repair of the building of the State Puppet Theater of Uzbekistan and its material and technical base No. 174 of August 28, 2017, No. 678 of August 28, 2017, No. 678 of Uzbekkonsert State Institution, January 5, 2018, No. 678 of January 5, 2018. on the program of measures to strengthen the material and technical base of theaters and develop their activities" No. 9, March 18, 2018 "Organizing the activities of the art palace in Termiz city and ensuring the effective use of other infrastructure facilities on" No. 204, dated January 10, 2019, "Ticket transactions No. 18, February 5, 2019, "On measures to strengthen the material and technical base and develop the activities of the State Philharmonic of Uzbekistan" No. 18 No. 88, dated March 30, 2019, dated March 30, 2019, dated March 30, 2019, dated March 30, 2019, dated April 18, 2019. on measures" No. 329, dated May 8, 2019 "On approval of the regulation on the procedure for payment of copyright for the creation of dramatic, musical and musical-dramatic works intended for public performance No. 385, dated September 5, 2019, No. 732, dated September 20, 2019, "On the organization of the activities of the Margilan city musical makom theater under the Uzbek national makom art center" "Tomosha" children's musical theater studio should be further improved No. 789, dated May 23, 2020, No. 325, dated May 23, 2020, "On improving the effectiveness of the marketing activities of museums and theaters in the Republic of Uzbekistan", dated November 30, 2020, "Organizing the activities of some state theaters in the Republic No. 754, on February 23, 2021, No. 98, 2021, No. 98, 2021 On April 23, 2021, No. 235 "On measures to hold the Eurasia International Theater Arts Festival", on May 27, 2021, "Organization of the Bukhara Palace of Culture and further promotion of theater art in the region" "On development measures" No. 329 [1] is the resolution. Ethical values, new understandings of the commonality of man and the world, history and modernity - today's Uzbek Theater attracts more and more. The increased interest in the fate of the National Theater,

Haydarov A. Culture is the foundation of national growth. - Tashkent: Golden Heritage Press. 2021. - B. 478.

closeness to life, and the new generation of viewers encourage theater artists to new research.[²]

Thanks to the support of the state, 39 professional theaters and theater studios are operating in our country today. Different genres - European-type drama, national musical drama, opera and ballet live and develop. There are puppet theaters in every region, Russian drama theaters and musical theaters in Fergana, Samarkand and Tashkent. Tashkent occupies a special place in the life of the republican theater. One third of the country's theaters and concert halls are located here, where performances are performed in Uzbek and Russian languages. Today, in the city of Tashkent, the State Academic Grand Theater of Uzbekistan named after Alisher Navoi, the State Musical Comedy (Operetta) Theater of Uzbekistan, the Uzbek National Academic Drama Theater, the State Drama Theater of Uzbekistan, the State Satire Theater of Uzbekistan, State Youth Theater of Uzbekistan, State Youth Theater of Uzbekistan, State Academic Russian Drama Theater of Uzbekistan, State Musical Theater of Uzbekistan named after Mukimi, Uzbek National Puppet Theater, Youth Experimental Theater "Diydor" studio" state institution, "Tomosha" children's musical theater-studio" state institution, "Peoples' Friendship" palace, Turkestan art palace are among them. It is worth noting that these theaters and concert palaces have become a field of experience in terms of art and organization. In these theaters, the branches of Uzbek Theater stand out with their loyalty to their traditions. At the same time, they are popular outside the country and warm hearts. It is worth noting that fundamental changes in the political, economic, social life and cultural processes that took place due to independence are clearly expressed on the stage of theaters, and the trends related to these changes are visible in stage life as well.

Theaters of Uzbekistan today are an integral part of the country's cultural life. A clear example of this is the fact that many directors, actors, and theater performances are receiving many prizes and awards at various pageants, festivals and contests. Every year, the Ministry of Culture organizes various district screenings, contests and festivals in various theaters in terms of themes and genres. Among them, the annual final reviews, which reward the most interesting solutions of playwrights, directors, actors, stenographers and composers, are of particular importance. Puppet theater festivals have become a tradition. Theaters and experts from different countries are invited to them as

² M.Sh.Qayimov, A.S.Umarov, U.G.Zunnunova. Art management. Study guide. "Yextremum-press". - Tashkent 2012, 375 B.

guests. The development of the art of opera and ballet in Uzbekistan was uneven: there were periods of stagnation as well as sharp upswings. However, despite these conflicts, positive trends are clearly visible in the history of the opera and Ballet Theater. It was during these years that many new aspects of it appeared.

The staging of many plays and the emergence of young talented artists or the creation of a number of operas and ballets that have arisen from research does not only mark this renewal. What is important is that the attitude towards the genre itself has changed significantly. In the modern sense, opera is paying more attention to the action of the musical stage. It is not just music on stage, but also a combination of music and stage creativity. It seems that the role of the stage manager of the performance has been exceeded. After all, the style and culture of stage interpretation depend on not only the images of the actors' characters, the behavior of the chorus and corps de ballet, but on the concept of the performance. Never before has the staging factor been so important for opera and Ballet Theater. In the modern world, management of concerts and entertainment events is becoming increasingly important in the field of culture and art. At the level of practical application, it began to form a long time ago when the need to organize mass actions and exhibitions arose. Regardless of the historical period and national traditions, the relationship between art and the audience always had to be managed. Every performance, concert (as well as other public entertainment events) should be organized accordingly. All participants should know their role, and the public should be informed about the time and place of the event and the rules of conduct adopted within it. If we talk about commercial events that show films, dramatic and musical performances, they need to organize very active advertising and ticket sales. Every aspect of a great cultural event, not to mention the event itself, requires profound leadership that has already existed in practice.

Today, management in the field of concerts and entertainment events is one of the directions of artistic management (art management). Management in art became the subject of research as an independent scientific direction only in the 20th century. This is primarily related to the active development of the general rules of the theory of management, which have recently taken their place in the system of scientific knowledge. At the same time, for many centuries, humankind has accumulated a lot of experience in creative activities that need theoretical understanding and generalization. Many scientific publications on

the subject of management in the field of art are a description of the existing experience.

At the same time, there are almost no authoritative and recognized theories in the field of art management by the scientific community: it can be noted that relevant theoretical ideas are in the process of formation. An activity in the field of art, like any other activity, should generate enough income to cover unavoidable expenses, even if it does not involve making a profit. Such an activity, like any other activity, presupposes the presence of "customers", conventionally called an audience or public. In other words, it satisfies existing social needs, and within its framework, resources - spiritual and material exchange - are carried out between all participants of this activity. From the point of view of organizing the production and sale of activity products, art management assumes the management of a process similar to any other production and other type of trade, therefore, art management is a general management science. At the same time, concert and entertainment management, as well as other areas of arts management, have a number of unique features specific to the arts. [3]

Unlike other types of management, the creative process is highly specific in terms of its organization, as well as the need to "sell" the result. Production and consumption of creative products - musical and literary works, theatrical and cinematographic products, does not have a number of specific characteristics with the consumption of products and services belonging to other fields of production activity, except for art and culture. As part of such specific features, there is a direct link between the very high level of risk associated with cultural and creative projects and the duration of creative product production and its final value, marketing strategy and pricing policy for the realization of artistic products with unique characteristics. It can be noted that there is no. Thus, the specific characteristics of creative activity (both from the production side and from the consumption side) have a great influence on the actual management processes, that is, artistic management. In order to understand the specifics of concert and entertainment management, it is first necessary to rely on general models that are characteristic of all management processes, regardless of their direction.

No matter how exceptional the features of management in the field of art are, they inevitably appear as a special case of general laws, that is, management as a system of organizing the production and sale of a specific product Like other

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types of theoretical understanding of management processes , the theory of management in the field of art also tries to explain the nature of management work, establishes connections between cause and effect, determines the factors and conditions under which the joint work of people is both useful and effective. Based on the points of view and principles of management, based on official documents and existing special studies, it is possible to determine the main content and goals of management in the field of art as a management activity.[⁴] The main directions of such activities, which are also characteristic of the management of concerts and entertainment events, are as follows: the effectiveness of the management of concert events is ensured by the unity of all types of management process: economic, organizational, technical and social-psychological. [⁵] At the same time, the economic side of management is the management of financial and economic aspects, the organizational-technical side is the management of production processes and the provision of resources, and the social-psychological side is the management of employees, as well as interaction with consumers of the final product. The short analyzes conducted show that the modern management of concerts and entertainment events, as a field of art management, is a complex structural complex that summarizes the goals and tasks, principles and functions, stages and stages of management activities from a theoretical point of view. Implementation allows creating and implementing various creative concerts and entertainment events, each of which fulfills its mission of social importance.

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